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Supplementary material for this article is available [online](#)

Abstract

During the 2024 Arctic summer, an unexpected sea ice patch ($\sim 100\,000\text{ km}^2$) survived in the western Chukchi Sea, an event that has not occurred in the past 20 years. Combining satellite data, PIOMAS model, and ERA5 reanalysis data, we analyze this anomaly's evolution and its dynamic and thermodynamic drivers in the 2000–2024 series. The analysis reveals that July–August are key months; ice concentration and thickness during this time determines the fate of the sea ice survival in September. Before July 2024, sea ice near Wrangel Island has experienced rapid and sustained thickening, with its distribution closely resembling the levels observed in 2000 and 2001 (the only other summers with ice survival). Persistent northerly winds east of Wrangel Island during the melt season contributed to sea ice thickening and played a crucial role in its survival. At the same time, a cooler-than-normal air temperature near Wrangel Island supported the stable presence of sea ice in this region. The study underscores that the 'New Arctic' conditions, namely thinning and increasingly mobile sea ice, raise the likelihood of unpredictable events of both unexpected sea ice survival and sudden loss.

1. Introduction

Under the trend of climate warming, the Arctic sea ice extent in September 2024 (4.8 million km^2) reached the fifth lowest level on record since satellite observations began in 1978. Surprisingly, during the month of minimum sea ice extent, a large and persistent patch of sea ice occurred between the far northeastern Siberian coast and Wrangel Island in the western Chukchi Sea (<https://nsidc.org/sea-ice-today/analyses/new-abnormal>). Starting in mid-July 2024, the ice surrounding this patch began to melt rapidly, exposing vast areas of open water. Despite the continued melting through mid-September, the ice area decreased, but a significant portion of the ice remained (figure 1). After the melting period

(May–September) ended, this unusual patch of ice survived this summer and will become second-year ice.

Satellite observations indicate that most of the ice in the Chukchi Sea is typically covered by first-year ice, i.e. the sea ice thickness (SIT) in this region usually represents the growth of sea ice during the freeze-up season. Over the past decades, the rate of decline in sea ice extent in the Chukchi Sea has accelerated (Frey *et al* 2015, Serreze *et al* 2016), and the Arctic has generally transitioned from thicker, more deformed ice to thinner, smoother ice (Krumpfen *et al* 2025). While thermodynamic processes are the primary drivers of sea ice changes, dynamic processes, particularly in the context of the transition to thinner, younger ice, must also be considered (Sumata *et al* 2023). The

Chukchi Sea, located at the edge of the Beaufort Gyre, is influenced by the movement of sea ice, which affects its ice condition (Zhang *et al* 2024). This has led to fluctuations and anomalies in sea ice extent, despite the overall rapid decline. The frequency and intensity of northeasterly winds may cause sea ice from the Beaufort Gyre to accumulate along the Siberian coast. As a result, the sea ice conditions along the land areas of the Chukchi Sea have become more complex (Frey *et al* 2015).

The SIT on both sides of Wrangel Island in the western Chukchi Sea shows a pronounced dipole phenomenon (Ross *et al* 2024). Its unique geographic position creates a narrow ice outlet along the Siberian coast for the sea ice circulation path. This provides ideal conditions for ice accumulation and thickening on the eastern side of the island. In contrast, the ice on the western side continues to drift away from the

island, forming an ice-free gap (Cavalieri and Martin 2012, Moore and Pickart 2012). The thicker sea ice on the eastern side seems to be the primary reason it can withstand summer melting (Chinn *et al* 2023). However, given the context of ‘New Arctic’ with thinner and younger sea ice (Kwok 2018, Parkinson and DiGirolamo 2021, Soleymani and Scott 2023, Sumata *et al* 2023, Muilwijk *et al* 2024, Song *et al* 2025), the unexpected sea ice survival near Wrangel Island in the western Chukchi Sea in summer 2024 attracts our attention (figure 1).

This raises the following questions, which are examined in this study: Considering the summer 2024 sea ice and wind conditions in context to the climatology (2002–2023), what was unusual? How have the spring–summer sea ice conditions in the western Chukchi Sea evolved over the past two decades? How did the sea ice conditions developed near Wrangel

Island in 2024, and what are the reasons, both from dynamic and thermodynamics perspectives, that the ice could survive.

The provided analysis of this rare sea ice survival event in summer 2024 contributes to a deeper understanding of the sea ice changes in the western Chukchi Sea and their drivers under the 'New Arctic' conditions. It also increases the awareness of the likelihood of unpredictable events, such as sudden ice disappearance, but also unexpected ice survival. This is important to improve model simulations and early warning systems, which can contribute to safer navigation in this region.

2. Data and methodology

We utilized the NSIDC Bootstrap sea ice concentration (SIC) dataset at 25 km resolution (Comiso 2023) for 2000 and 2001, and the ASI SIC dataset provided by the University of Bremen at 6.25 km resolution from 2002 to 2024 (Spren *et al* 2008) to construct a continuous time series of SIC covering our study period from 2000 to 2024. Ice drift data from the NSIDC Polar Pathfinder Daily 25 km EASE-grid sea ice motion vectors (version 4) (Tschudi *et al* 2019) was adopted, spanning from 2000 to 2023, augmented by data for 2024 from the OSI SAF (62.5 km resolution) (Saf 2010). The PIOMAS SIT dataset (25 km resolution) from 1979 to the present (Zhang and Rothrock 2003) was used to quantitatively assess SIT dynamics near Wrangel Island. Additionally, SIT derived from CryoSat-2 data (2010–2024) was employed to assist in evaluating PIOMAS SIT (Kurtz and Harbeck 2017). Besides, we applied the ECMWF ERA5 reanalysis monthly data, including 2 m temperature and 10 m wind speed and direction at 0.25° horizontal resolution (Hersbach *et al* 2020) to explore atmospherically driven causing factors.

Finally, multi-source high-resolution remote sensing data were used to observe the sea ice surface conditions of the surviving sea ice in 2024 during different months, including Sentinel-1 SAR data and ICESat-2 ATL07 sea ice surface height data (Kwok *et al* 2019). The SAR images were processed to obtain backscatter values following the removal of thermal noise and speckle-filter, using the Sentinel Application Platform for calibration. By combining SAR backscatter coefficients and ATL07 sea ice surface height data, an initial assessment can be made of the ice surface condition (e.g. sea ice ridges) and the accumulation state of the sea ice along the coast of East Siberia. Landsat 9 optical data were also utilized, from which the ice surface temperature was retrieved using the thermal infrared bands. Specifically, the normalized difference water index is used to classify ice and water. The split-window algorithm is then applied to retrieve the sea ice and water surface temperatures,

with the effective emissivity for each channel derived from the TIRS spectral response function and the ASTER spectral library (accessed at <http://speclib.jpl.nasa.gov/>, accessed on 15 September 2024) (Song *et al* 2023). Additionally, MODIS optical imagery is used to visually display the sea ice extent in the study area during the summers of 2000, 2001, and 2024. The data used in this study are reprojected to the EPSG 3413 Polar Stereographic projection.

3. Results

3.1. Anomalous sea ice during the 2024 melt season

The historical review of SIC since 2000 shows that the last time sea ice survived near Wrangel Island in the western Chukchi Sea (region outlined in red in figure 1) in September before 2024 was in 2000 and 2001 (figure 2(a)). In the last 22 years from 2002 to 2023, there was no sea ice on the southeastern side of Wrangel Island in September until this year in 2024. Accordingly, we chose the period 2002–2023 as the background reference. This region has remained nearly fully ice-covered during the winter months (figure S1), but the SIC shows a pronounced year-to-year fluctuation between June and July from 2002 to 2012, with a significant decline after 2012. It then started to recover around 2019 until it reached a new anomalous high SIC in summer 2024 (figure 2(a)). Optical remote sensing imagery offers a clear comparison of sea ice distribution in 2000, 2001, and 2024 (figure 2(c)). In July 2024, SIC was significantly larger than in 2000 and 2001, with ice accumulating along the Siberian coast. The increase in SIC during the melting season suggests that more ice was able to resist melting in August and September 2024 (figures 2(a) and (b)).

The analysis of SIT reveals the continuous anomalous thickening of sea ice from May to July 2024, compared to the long-term (2002–2023) mean, which was critical to its survival in 2024 (figures 2(d) and S2, S3). In April 2024, the SIT distribution resembled that of the long-term (2002–2023) mean, i.e. those of years with no sea ice in September. After May, the sea ice entered the melting phase. During the subsequent melting period, a noticeable slowdown in the melting was observed in June and July, as indicated by a significant shift of the SIT distribution towards larger values, compared to the long-term (2002–2023) mean (figure 2(d)). An according shift was also observed in the other anomalous ice-covered years 2000 and 2001. Enough accumulation completed before July brought the 2024 SIT close to that of 2000 and 2001. This allowed the cluster of isolated ice to resist the final stages of melting after July 2024 and survive into September (figures 2 and S2). From the analysis of the SIC and SIT evolution, we can conclude that particularly July and August are the key months, as the

Figure 2. Evolution of sea ice concentration (SIC) and thickness (SIT) near Wrangel Island in the western Chukchi Sea (region outlined in red in figure 1) from 2000 to 2024. (a) Year-to-year variability of monthly SIC from May to September; for selected periods in June–July, the change of SIC per year (‘slope’) is given; (b) daily mean SIC variations over the annual cycle for each year, with the black dashed line representing the long-term mean (2002–2023) SIC; anomalous years are highlighted (red: 2024, dark blue: 2000, light blue: 2001); (c) MODIS true-color optical imagery showing the spatial distribution of sea ice in July during the anomalous years when sea ice persisted (2000, 2001, 2024); (d) histograms of daily SIT from April to September for the anomalous years, compared to the long-term statistics, based on PIOMAS dataset.

ice conditions during this time determine the survival of sea ice in September.

3.2. Drivers of anomalous sea ice changes in 2024

The first candidate to explain the anomalous regional summer sea ice survival is the anomalous wind-driven ice drift. To explore this, figure 3 shows the spatial distribution of SIC, SIT, drift, and near-surface wind field around Wrangel Island from June to September. Compared to the long-term (2002–2023) mean, significant differences in the wind field were observed around Wrangel Island in June and July 2024, with strong northerly winds directed towards the Siberian coast. As a result, sea ice accumulated in the south, particularly along the Siberian coast, leading to the thickening of the ice near the coast. This accumulation resulted in anomalous high SIC and SIT in June and July 2024.

This contrasts with the mean sea ice drift observed from 2002 to 2023, where despite ice accumulation towards Wrangel Island, no similar accumulation

occurred along the Siberian coast. In 2024, the sea ice accumulation along the Siberian coast was much stronger than climatologically normal, as the southward drifted sea ice was nearly blocked by the coastline. High-resolution imagery and sea ice surface height data from ICESat-2 altimetry clearly show this thickened (and dirty) ice along the Siberian coast and SAR data also show a large number of ice ridges on the sea ice surface (figure S4). These northerly wind patterns were also observed in July–August 2000 and 2001 (figure S5). However, in June of 2000 and 2001, the wind direction was southerly (figure S5(a) and (i)), almost the exact opposite of June 2024 (figure 3(i)). As a result, in July of 2000 and 2001, sea ice accumulated around Wrangel Island, while in 2024, it concentrated along the Siberian coast (figure 2(c)).

In August 2024, the wind direction around Wrangel Island shifted, northerly winds persisted and easterly winds transitioned to westerly winds. This caused coastal sea ice to move southward and

gradually become isolated as it entered the final phase of melting in September (figure 3). The wind field anomaly in August and September is linked to the collapse of the Beaufort High (figure S6), a phenomenon discussed previously (Petty *et al* 2016, Moore *et al* 2018a). Furthermore, figure 3 indicates that the wind speed near Wrangel Island in September 2024 was lower than the long-term (2002–2023) mean, which protected sea ice from break-up and contributed to its survival during the melt season.

Lower-than-usual air temperatures were observed in the study region in 2024. During summer, the 2 m temperature near Wrangel Island was approximately 2 K lower than the long-term (2002–2023) mean (figure 4). Particularly, from June 2024 onwards, temperatures along the Siberian coast were significantly lower (figures 4(b)–(e)), which

is associated with the accumulated sea ice along the coast. Both the increased SIC and SIT limited the heat exchange between the ocean and the atmosphere.

The frozen season in the Chukchi Sea typically lasts until early May, after which the sea ice edge begins to retreat northward (Frey *et al* 2015). However, the timeseries of SIC in the study area shows that the sea ice extent began to decline later in 2024 than in previous years (figure 2(b)), corresponding to lower temperatures (figure 4(a)). From June to July, sea ice rapidly melted and thinned, but lower temperatures starting in June slowed the melting in 2024 compared to the long-term (2002–2023) mean. During the typically intense melting period of July and August, persistent strong northerly winds (figure 3(j)) pushed the thinning sea ice directly toward the coast of Eastern Siberia, where

it accumulated and resisted further melting. By this time, the SIT distribution had closely resembled that of 2000 and 2001 (figure 2(d)). Consequently, a combination of dynamic processes, such as ice drift and ridging, and thermodynamic processes, including anomalously cool conditions, contributed to the survival of sea ice over the summer in this region.

4. Discussion and conclusion

In mid-September 2024, a remarkable amount of sea ice was observed near Wrangel Island, a phenomenon not seen in the western Chukchi Sea in nearly two decades. Our analysis indicates that the accumulation and thickening of sea ice along the coast due to dynamic processes was likely the main reason for its survival, supported by reduced melting due to reduced ocean-atmosphere energy exchange and cooler-than-average temperatures.

This rare sea ice survival in September was only observed 20 years earlier, in 2000 and 2001 (figure 2). Our comparison shows that the same mechanism triggered these extremely rare sea ice anomalies during these two years as in 2024. The figure further shows that after the last occurrence of sea ice survival in 2001, SIC showed substantial year-to-year fluctuations in June and July from 2002 to 2012. After a sharp decline afterwards, SIC began to recover around 2019, peaking in the summer of 2024. Similarly, SIT began to rebound in March to July around 2020 (figure S3). This trend aligns with enhanced sea ice dynamics caused by thinner ice in the ‘New Arctic’ (Sprenn *et al* 2011, Zhang *et al* 2012, Li *et al* 2022,

Aue and Rinke 2023). Besides, a similar temporal pattern of lower-than-normal 2 m temperature can be found in the summer months for 2000 and 2001 (figure 4(a)). But, after September 2024, the temperature curve goes back to the warm track in the ‘New Arctic’.

The large-scale dirtying of the sea ice surface in 2024 (figures 2(c) and S4) was not a special occurrence. Sea ice in the Chukchi Sea typically harbors significant phytoplankton growth on its underside (Pickart *et al* 2024) and with frequent ice collisions and accumulation, phytoplankton on the ice underside becomes exposed, along with algae growth in ridges, causing the ice surface to appear dark green (Fernández-Méndez *et al* 2018). This further confirms the strong accumulation and deformation processes of sea ice in this region.

It should be noted that the PIOMAS model is not a coupled model, and thus it cannot fully capture the air-sea interactions, which may lead to biases in the predicted SIT (Moore *et al* 2018b). Nevertheless, PIOMAS was able to accurately simulate the survival of the sea ice in such anomalous years as September 2000, 2001, and 2024, and the simulated ice extent and distribution were consistent with the observed SIC (figures 3 and S5). This offers valuable insight for early predictions of SIC and SIT near Wrangel Island in the western Chukchi Sea during the summer months. This area is a crucial route for the heavily trafficked Northeast Passage (Rodríguez *et al* 2024), and changes in ice conditions may have implications for vessel navigation safety and fuel consumption. Additionally, the absence of ice along the Siberian

coast provides a longer open-water period, which affects the movement and activities of marine animals, such as walrus (Jay *et al* 2012).

This paper examines both thermodynamic and dynamic factors influencing the sea ice survival in the western Chukchi Sea in 2024. However, it does not provide a quantitative analysis of their relative role during the melting season in this anomalous year. Future studies could use sea ice drift data to calculate the contribution of ice drift and convergence along the Chukchi Sea coastline to its resistance to melting (Li *et al* 2022). A better understanding of the mechanisms behind sea ice changes and extreme events in this region under the 'New Arctic' conditions will help in adjusting/improving models for more accurate regional predictions of sea ice conditions (e.g. Bushuk *et al* 2017). Another future research could assess longer timeseries datasets to compare the likelihood of sea ice survival in summer in the study region during 'Old Arctic' vs. 'New Arctic' conditions, and to investigate potential decadal signals (e.g. related to the Arctic Oscillation and Pacific Decadal Oscillation) in regional sea ice changes in the western Chukchi Sea.

Data availability statement

SIC data access from the National Snow and Ice Data Center (<https://nsidc.org/data/nsidc-0079/versions/4>) and the University of Bremen (www.seaice.uni-bremen.de/sea-ice-concentration/amsre-amsr2/). Ice motion data are available from the National Snow and Ice Data Center (<https://nsidc.org/data/nsidc-0079/versions/4>) and Ocean and Sea Ice Satellite Application Facility (<https://osi-saf.eumetsat.int/products/osi-405-d>). PIOMAS model ice thickness fields are obtained from the Polar Science Center, Applied Physics Laboratory, University of Washington (http://psc.apl.uw.edu/research/projects/arctic-sea-ice-volume-anomaly/data/model_grid). Monthly mean wind and 2 m temperature data from the ERA5 reanalysis are available on the Climate Data Store through the Copernicus Climate Change Service (<https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/datasets/reanalysis-era5-single-levels-monthly-means?tab=overview>).

MODIS true-color imagery is obtained from the NASA Worldview application (<https://worldview.earthdata.nasa.gov>). Sentinel-1 SAR data in Extra Wide Swath mode (HH/HV polarization) were sourced from the Copernicus Open Access Hub (<https://scihub.copernicus.eu>). Landsat-9 has been downloaded from the USGS website (<https://earthexplorer.usgs.gov/>). ICESat-2 ATL07 sea ice height product is available through the National Snow and Ice Data Center (NSIDC) and is accessible online at <https://nsidc.org/data/rdef4/versions/1>.

All data that support the findings of this study are included within the article (and any supplementary files).

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

Author contributions

Conceptualization: Jiaxing Gong, Lijuan Song, Xi Zhao, Annette Rinke, Xiaoyu Wang;

Data curation: Jiaxing Gong, Lijuan Song, Yifan Wu, Bo Li, Xiaoyu Wang;

Formal analysis: Jiaxing Gong, Lijuan Song, Yifan Wu.

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